

DEVELOPMENT OF NOVEL AND HIGH-THROUGHPUT DIAGNOSTIC PROCEDURES TO DETECT *XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA* (XF) IN PLANTA

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The development of novel diagnostic procedures to detect *Xylella fastidiosa* is attempted by two different methodical approaches: a serological rapid test (immunostrip or LF assay) and a molecular method, based on a sandwich type DNA-hybridization assay (NALF). Both assays will allow fast, easy and direct detection of the bacteria in the field without the need of a laboratory.

Specific Oligos have been designed and optimized for the development of the NALF, meeting the special requirements of the test system. Conjugation protocols for labelling of Oligos to gold nanoparticles have been evaluated and the reaction between the immobilized capture oligos and the Oligo-gold conjugate using a *Xylella fastidiosa* specific ss-DNA as positive control has been demonstrated, with a detection limit of $1.2 \cdot 10^{10}$ molecules. So far the method failed to detect genomic DNA of *Xf* or a *Xf* PCR amplicon and further optimization experiments for Oligo conjugation and PCR conditions are carried out. For immunostrip (LF) development on a serological base, a new antiserum against *Xylella fastidiosa* was produced and IgGs from different bleedings have been evaluated in DAS-ELISA. While detecting six tested *Xf* subspecies so far, the new antiserum exhibits an increased specificity towards *Xf* CoDiRO, especially in terms of detection limit. A lateral flow prototype has been produced and specificity, cross reaction and healthy background reactions have been tested, with results being in agreement with ELISA data. *Xylella fastidiosa* from infected olive branches could easily be detected in both LF and ELISA and a demonstration video has been prepared.